

(>1,500 mm). Rice in the savanna ripens under higher solar radiation.

Panicles/m² were similar for all varieties tested (Table 2). All varieties

were semidwarf (110 cm).

Both SiPi 692033 and FARO 27 have high amylose content (>25%) with hard

gel consistency (26-35 mm). SiPi 692033 has long, slender grains and higher yield than FARO 27. □

Seed technology

Influence of *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Sawada on rice seed germination and seedling vigor

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We studied the influence of *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams and D. Hawksw. (syn. *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Sawada) on seed germination and seedling vigor of seven rice varieties. Seeds were thoroughly washed with sterile distilled water and 10 seeds were later on moistened filter paper in a petri dish, with 10 replications. The

Influence of *Acrocyndrium oryzae* on seed germination and rice seedling vigor. Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

Cultivar	Seed germination (%)		Seedling vigor ^a							
	Healthy	Inoculated	Shoot length (mm)				Root length (mm)			
			Day 4		Day 7		Day 4		Day 7	
			NI	I	NI	I	NI	I	NI	I
IET9233	95	93	15.3	10.7	32.4	29.1	14.6	13.9	32.2	29.1
ET8611	89	84	6.6	4.8	19.1	18.7	16.2	14.8	33.0	31.3
IET8584	96	92	5.3	3.6	25.9	25.2	15.0	13.2	30.4	30.3
IR62	90	87	4.8	3.6	15.4	7.8	12.0	10.3	29.6	27.2
AU1	90	86	10.5	7.3	26.1	23.1	20.3	17.2	59.9	47.2
J58	92	89	7.6	6.3	33.5	24.7	15.7	13.6	41.8	40.4
ADT37	94	91	4.3	3.6	9.7	1.9	16.8	15.6	44.0	39.3
LSD (P = 0.05)	4.34		2.35				3.42			

^a NI = not inoculated, I = inoculated.

seeds were sprayed with a 4×10^6 spores/ml suspension of the fungus. (Control seeds were sprayed with sterile distilled water.) Seed germination and seedling vigor were assessed 4 and 7 d

after inoculation.

Inoculation considerably reduced seed germination in all varieties (see table). Shoot and root lengths of all the rices also were reduced. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Boiling water treatment to improve germination of *Sesbania rostrata*

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The hard seed coat in *Sesbania rostrata* can be broken by treating seeds with concentrated sulfuric acid for 40 min. However, sulfuric acid is costly and requires care. Dormancy due to hard seed coat in many legumes could be

Germination of *S. rostrata* seeds treated with boiling water (98 °C). Dharwad, India, 1988.

Treatment	Germination (%) at indicated period after treatment				
	3 d	4 d	5 d	6 d	7 d
Control (no boiling water)	2	4	4	4	4
Treatment with 98 °C water					
15 s	34	40	50	62	62
30 s	42	52	54	70	70
45 s	42	52	60	72	76
60 s	52	66	66	74	76
75 s	42	60	66	78	78
90 s	54	62	62	70	72 (4) ^a
120 s	64	76	76	76	76 (8)
150 s	50	60	60	60	60 (10)
180 s	50	68	68	68	68 (10)

^a Figures in parentheses = percent deformed seeds.